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Civic and Political Participation in the Italian Regions During the Period 2011-2022

It decreased on average by 5.44%

Istat calculates civic and political participation in the Italian regions. The variable is defined as the percentage of people aged 14 and over who carry out at least one civic and political participation activity out of the total number of people aged 14 and over. The activities considered are: talking about politics at least once a week; inform yourself about the facts of Italian politics at least once a week; participate online in consultations or votes on social (civic) or political problems (e.g. urban planning, signing a petition) at least once in the 3 months preceding the interview; express opinions on social or political issues through websites or social media at least once in the 3 months preceding the interview.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of civic and political participation in 2022. Friuli Venezia Giulia is in first place for the value of civic and political participation in 2022 with a value of 72.4, followed by Trentino Alto Adige with an amount of 72.1 and Veneto with a value of 70.00 units. In the middle of the table are Abruzzo with an amount of 66.3 units, followed by Lazio with a value of 66 units and Piedmont with 65.7 units. Basilicata closes the ranking with an amount of 52.1 units, Basilicata with 51.1 units and Calabria with an amount of 49.2 units.

Ranking of the regions by value of the percentage change in civic and political participation between 2011 and 2022. Abruzzo is in first place by value of the percentage change in civic and political participation with an amount equal to +3.92% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 63.80 units in 2011 up to a value of 66.30 units in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige follows with a variation equal to -0.28% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 72.30 units in 2011 up to a value of 72.10 units in 2022. Campania follows with a variation from an amount of -0.35% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 57.10 units in 2011 up to a value of 56, 90 units in 2022. In the middle of the table are Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation equal to -4.49% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 75.80 units up to 72.40 units between 2011 and 2022. Continued Veneto with a variation equal to -6.98% corresponding to a variation from 74.50 units in 2011 up to 659.30 units in 2022. Sardinia closes the ranking with a value of -9.78% equal to a variation from an amount of 71.60 units in 21011 up to a value of 64.60 units in 2022. Umbria follows with a variation of -9.87% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 71.90 units in 2011 up to to 64.60 units in 2022. Basilicata closes the ranking with a variation of -9.88% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 56.70 units in 2011 up to a value of 51.10 units in 2022. On average the value of civic and political participation decreased in the Italian regions between 66.95 units in 2011 up to a value of 63.30 units in 2022 equal to -5.44%.

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Civic and political participation in the Italian macro-regions between 2011 and 2022. The value of civic and political participation decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2011 and 2022. In particular, civic and political participation suffered the following variations namely: -3.67% in Southern Italy, Southern Italy with -4.00%, Islands with -4.98%, Central Italy with -5.55%, North-East with -5.77%, North with -7.07%, North-West with -8.10%. Even if the value of civic and political participation has decreased in all Italian macro-regions, there are still significant differences between Southern and Central-Northern Italy. In fact, the value of civic and political participation in Southern Italy is 17.00% lower than the corresponding value in Central Italy, 21.5% lower than in the North-East, 19.3% lower in the North and 17% lower .6 compared to the North-West.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with the k-Means algorithm with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Tuscany, Trentino Alto Adige, Piedmont, Lombardy, Liguria, Umbria, Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lazio, Veneto, Sardinia, Marche, Valle d'Aosta, Abruzzo;
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Campania, Calabria, Puglia, Basilicata, Molise.

Considering the value of the average of the clusters it turns out that the value of Cluster 1 is much higher than the value of Cluster 2 or $C1 > C2$. It follows that the value of civic and political participation in the regions of Central-Northern Italy is significantly higher than the corresponding value in the Southern regions. However, two southern regions have high values of civic and political participation and are such that they can participate in Cluster 1. These regions are Abruzzo and Sardinia.

Conclusions. Civic and political participation decreased significantly in the Italian regions and macro-regions between 2011 and 2022. If we consider the average value of civic and political participation in the Italian regions, an essentially fluctuating trend emerges. Between 2011 and 2013 there was a growth in the value of civic and political participation in the Italian regions, reaching the absolute maximum of the period with an amount equal to 68.92%. Between 2013 and 2019 there was a significant reduction of the value of civic and political participation going from an amount of 69.82 up to the absolute minimum of 58.1 units. Between 2019 and 2021 the value of civic and political participation grew and then decreased marginally in 2022, settling at around the value of 63.3 units. Abruzzo is the only Italian region where there was a growth in the value of civic and political participation between 2011 and 2022 with a +3.92%. Furthermore, in the generalized reduction in the value of civic and political participation, a significant difference persists between southern regions with low values of the observed variable and northern regions with high values.

Italians' interest in politics therefore significantly decreased between 2011 and 2022. We can note that during the Covid 19 period, i.e. between 2020 and 2021, there was a recovery in civic and political participation in the Italian regions. The behavior of Italians towards political issues appears to be in contradiction with the traditional vision of Italians as a people made up of significant political and party connections. Italians have less and less interest in politics and participate less and less in political phenomena both at party level and at the level of political dialogue and debate. It is very likely that social networks have played a significant role in distancing Italians from the political debate. In fact, in social networks, lifestyle topics are dominant compared to content aimed at political and civic education. It follows that Italians have fewer opportunities to participate in political phenomena and to obtain political information. The consequence of this growth in ignorance and disinterest in political issues consists in the growth of abstentionism and the distance between a class of professional politicians and a population devoid of democratic instruments of control. Since democratic systems function thanks to the control that informed, participating and interested citizens exercise over the activities of politicians, it follows that the degree of effectiveness of democracy in Italy decreased between 2011 and 2022. Furthermore, the quality of political personnel demonstrates

such decay of the political capacity of the Italian people or the Italian nation. In fact, current Italian politicians have nothing to do with the politicians of the past, be they Christian Democrats, Communists, Socialists, Radicals, Liberals. And anyone who compares some speeches of the Italian political ruling class in the period 1946-1978 with those of 2011-2022 can find confirmation of how little content characterizes the current Italian ruling class, be it right-wing, centre-left or left-wing. . It is therefore necessary to intervene with incentives to ensure that political parties and movements that have parliamentary and government representation can invest in the training and information of the Italian population from a political point of view. For example, each parliamentary group could be asked to establish a foundation that can promote the ideas, values and political thought that inspires it through online and real-life training courses and also through the creation of communication tools that also consider the new media. In fact, one of the objectives of parliamentarians and the government should be to increase political and civic participation in the reduction of abstentionism and in the growth of the democratic pact between the population and institutions.

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Appendix

Macro-Regioni	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
<i>Nord</i>	73,5	73,3	74,5	72	71,5	68,3	64	63,9	62,5	68	69,4	68,3
<i>Nord-ovest</i>	72,8	72,9	72,8	69,9	70,8	67,6	62,4	63,7	61,9	67,1	68,8	66,9
<i>Nord-est</i>	74,5	73,8	76,8	75	72,4	69,3	66,2	64,3	63,4	69,1	70,3	70,2
<i>Centro</i>	70,3	68,8	73,4	71,9	71,3	67,9	64,2	61,7	60,9	65,2	70,4	66,4
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	57,5	57,9	58,4	57,4	56,7	53,3	50,5	50,3	50	51,1	55,6	55,2
<i>Sud</i>	57,2	55,9	57,6	56,9	55,5	52,2	49,9	50,3	49,7	50,5	55,9	55,1
<i>Isole</i>	58,2	61,9	60,1	58,5	59,2	55,6	51,7	50,3	50,8	51,8	55,1	55,3

	2011	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Trentino-Alto Adige	72.3	72.1	-0.2	-0.28
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	75.8	72.4	-3.4	-4.49
Abruzzo	63.8	66.3	2.5	3.92
Veneto	74.7	70	-4.7	-6.29
Emilia-Romagna	74.5	69.3	-5.2	-6.98
Liguria	75.5	69.6	-5.9	-7.81
Marche	67.9	66.6	-1.3	-1.91
Lazio	69	66	-3	-4.35
Toscana	72.9	67.1	-5.8	-7.96
Valle d'Aosta	65.5	64	-1.5	-2.29
Lombardia	73.1	67	-6.1	-8.34
Piemonte	71.5	65.7	-5.8	-8.11
Umbria	71.9	64.8	-7.1	-9.87
Sardegna	71.6	64.6	-7	-9.78
Molise	61	59	-2	-3.28
Campania	57.1	56.9	-0.2	-0.35
Sicilia	53.7	52.2	-1.5	-2.79
Puglia	56.5	52.1	-4.4	-7.79
Basilicata	56.7	51.1	-5.6	-9.88
Calabria	53.9	49.2	-4.7	-8.72

